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Effects of Population Growth Rate, Poverty and COVID-19 on Economic Growth in Africa (2020-2022). A panel regression Approach

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Abstract

Africa, a continent marked by its rich cultural diversity and abundant natural resources, has long grappled with several challenges influencing its economic growth. However, in recent times, the confluence of rapid population growth, persistent poverty, and the disruptive impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has posed unprecedented challenges to the region's sustainable development and economic growth. This study examined the effect of population growth rate, poverty, and COVID-19 on economic growth in Africa spanning from 2020-2022. The expo factor research design was used. Secondary data on population growth rate, poverty COVID-19 economic growth was sourced from World Bank Development Indicators website from 36 African countries. A panel regression technique was used to analyse the data with the aid of Eview-10.0 software. Both the pooled OLS, fixed effect, random effect, and Hausman test were estimated. The result indicated that Poverty and COVID-19 have a negative and significant impact on economic growth in Africa. Population growth rate has a negative but insignificant impact on economic growth in Africa. The study recommended the need to design and implement targeted poverty alleviation programs. These initiatives should aim to improve access to education, healthcare, and employment opportunities for impoverished communities. Additionally, providing skill development and entrepreneurship training can empower individuals to contribute to the economy. Considering the adverse impact of COVID-19 on economic growth, African nations should prioritize strengthening their healthcare infrastructure and pandemic preparedness. This involves investing in the healthcare sector, improving access to vaccines and medical resources, and establishing robust public health systems. Additionally, fostering international collaboration for knowledge sharing and resource distribution can aid in mitigating the negative economic effects of future health crises.

Keywords: Africa, COVID-19, Economic Growth, Population Growth Rate, Poverty.

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Introduction

Africa, a continent marked by its rich cultural diversity and vast natural resources, stands at a critical juncture in its socio-economic trajectory. As the second most populous continent, Africa's demographic landscape is characterized by a rapidly growing population. This demographic shift, coupled with persistent poverty challenges and the unprecedented global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, has ignited a complex interplay of factors influencing economic growth (Chang, Mohsin & Iqbal, 2023).

The population growth rate in Africa has been a subject of considerable scholarly and policy discourse. Over the past few decades, the continent has experienced significant demographic changes, with projections indicating that its population will continue to rise substantially in the coming years. The implications of such demographic dynamics extend beyond sheer numbers, delving into critical areas such as labor markets, education, healthcare, and, most significantly, economic development (Zinkina & Korotayev, 2014).

Poverty, a longstanding issue in many African nations, adds another layer of complexity to the economic landscape. Despite notable economic growth in certain regions, a substantial proportion of the population continues to grapple with poverty, hindering the equitable distribution of resources and opportunities. The intricate relationship between population growth, poverty, and economic development warrants meticulous examination to understand how these factors interact and shape the continent's future (Adeyeye, et al, 2023).

In the backdrop of these challenges, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has cast a long shadow over Africa's economic prospects. The continent's vulnerability to health crises is magnified by pre-existing economic and social disparities. The pandemic has not only strained healthcare systems but has also triggered disruptions in global supply chains, impacting trade, investment, and employment – elements crucial to sustained economic growth (Aditya & Amri, 2023).

This study aims to unravel the intricate web of relationships between population growth rate, poverty, and the COVID-19 pandemic, and their combined impact on economic growth in Africa. By delving into the nuanced dynamics at play, we seek to contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead for the continent. In doing so, we hope to inform policy discussions and provide valuable insights for crafting strategies that foster inclusive and resilient economic development across Africa.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to examine the effects of population growth rate, poverty, and COVID-19 on economic growth in Africa ranging from 2020-2022. Specifically, the study seeks to;

- Find out the impact of population growth rate on economic growth in Africa
- Examine the impact of poverty on economic growth in Africa
- Ascertain the impact of COVID-19 on economic growth in Africa

Hypothesis of the Study

The following null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance

- Population growth rate has no significant impact on economic growth in Africa

- Poverty has no significant impact on economic growth in Africa
- COVID-19 has no significant impact on economic growth in Africa

Theoretical Review

The following theories related to population growth rate, poverty, and economic growth were reviewed below

Demographic Dividend Theory

The theory was propounded by John C. Caldwell and John B. Casterline in 1993. This theory suggests that if a country experiences a decline in fertility rates, it can potentially benefit from a "demographic dividend." This occurs when the proportion of working-age individuals in the population is larger than the dependent youth and elderly population. With effective policies, this demographic structure can lead to increased productivity, economic growth, and improved living standards.

Dependency Theory

The theory was propounded by Raúl Prebisch and Hans Singer (1950s-1960s). Dependency theory argues that the economic development of less developed countries, such as many in Africa, is hindered by their dependence on more developed nations. The theory contends that this dependence contributes to poverty and can exacerbate the impact of factors like population growth and health crises on economic growth.

Demographic Transition Theory

The theory was propounded by Warren Thompson and Frank Notestein in the Mid-20th century. The Demographic Transition Theory posits that societies go through predictable stages of population growth as they undergo economic development. Initially, both birth and death rates are high, resulting in slow population growth. With economic development, death rates decline due to improved healthcare, leading to rapid population growth. Ultimately, as societies advance, birth rates also decline, stabilizing the population. This theory suggests that the demographic transition can impact economic growth through changes in the labor force and dependency ratios.

Malthusian Theory

The theory was propounded by Thomas Malthus in the Late 18th century. Malthusian theory argues that the population tends to grow exponentially while the means of subsistence grow arithmetically. According to Malthus, population growth would eventually outstrip the ability to produce enough food, leading to a "Malthusian crisis" marked by famine and poverty. While this theory has been criticized, it raises concerns about the sustainability of population growth concerning resource availability and economic development.

Structural Transformation Theory

The theory was propounded by W. Arthur Lewis and Rostow (1950s-1960s). This theory suggests that economic development involves a structural transformation from traditional agrarian economies to industrialized ones. In the process, surplus labor from agriculture moves to more productive sectors, fostering economic growth. However, challenges arise if the rate of population growth exceeds the pace of structural transformation, potentially leading to increased poverty and unemployment.

Inclusive Growth Theory

The Theory was propounded by Joseph Stiglitz et al in the Late 20th-century Overview: Inclusive growth theory emphasizes that for economic development to be sustainable, it must be inclusive, benefiting a broad section of the population. High population growth, if not accompanied by inclusive economic policies, can exacerbate poverty. In the context of COVID-19, inclusive growth becomes even more crucial to ensure that the benefits of recovery reach all segments of the population

Empirical Review of Literature

The empirical reviewed studies collectively contribute valuable insights into the complex relationships between the COVID-19 pandemic, poverty, population growth, and economic growth, offering recommendations for policymakers and international organizations.

Asare and Barfi (2021) evaluate the pandemic's impact on poverty alleviation and global GDP across 170 countries, considering individual effects. Employed econometric panel techniques (OLS, robust least squares) on data from Our World indata.com, including COVID-19 cases, deaths, stringency index, human development index, and GDP per capita. The findings revealed that stringency and disease contraction inversely affected poverty and economic growth. Surprisingly, recorded deaths had a positive impact. Recommends controlling population growth and investing in health, education, and economic stimulation.

Zineb, Zineb, and Ikram (2022) assess COVID-19 repercussions on population, GDP, logistics, and ISO 9001 certification in South Africa, Morocco, and Tunisia. Applied Grey Relational Grade (GRG) modeling and the maximin approach, using 2021 data from various sources. The findings indicated that the pandemic significantly impacted the population, GDP and logistics. South Africa was most affected, revealing negative correlations between COVID-19 and logistics. Recommends urgent interventions to protect economic systems.

Zhu, Bashir, and Marie (2022) Investigate the impact of income inequality and poverty on economic development in Vietnam from 1990 to 2016. Used econometric estimations, confirming a long-run association between inequality, poverty, and economic growth. Negative impact concentrated at high poverty levels. Advocates for poverty reduction policies, emphasizing their positive impact on economic growth.

Mahtta et al. (2022): Examine urban land expansion's relation to population and economic growth for 300+ cities globally. Used a large-scale study testing the importance of urban population and GDP growth in affecting urban land expansion. The findings revealed that population growth consistently dominated urban land expansion during 1970–2014. GDP growth became more important after 2000, especially in countries with strong governance. Governance quality is crucial for economic growth to affect urban land expansion.

Gagnon, Kamin, and Kearns (2023) examine COVID-19's effect on global real GDP, distinguishing between domestic and global trade variables. Used panel data regressions on 90 countries for 2020 Q1 to 2021 Q4. COVID-19 deaths had a small effect; lockdown stringency significantly influenced GDP. Economic effects varied between rich and poor countries, with global trade as a significant channel. Highlights the vulnerability of countries to both medical and economic contagion in a globalized world.

Byaro, et al (2023) Explore the effect of population growth on domestic investments in 45 Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. Applied Quantile Method of Moments with fixed effects, controlling for trade, HIV/AIDS prevalence, and economic growth. The findings indicated that rapid population growth

positively affected domestic investments in SSA. Trade was positive across all quantiles, while disease risks, like HIV/AIDS prevalence, slowed investment increases. Recommends addressing population challenges for long-term investments.

Methodology

This study used an ex post facto research design. Ex post facto research design, also known as causal-comparative research design, is a type of research design where the researcher examines the effects of an independent variable that cannot be manipulated for ethical or practical reasons. Unlike experimental research, where the researcher actively manipulates variables, ex post facto research involves observing and analysing the consequences of naturally occurring events or conditions (Taff, 2020). This study used secondary data; the data were sourced from the World Development Indicators website. The study covered from 2020-2022 in 36 African countries, namely Angola, Burundi, Benin, Botswana, Central African Republic, Cote d'Ivoire, Cameroon, Congo, Democratic Republic, Congo, Comoros, Cabo Verde, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Madagascar, Mali, Mozambique, Mauritius, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Eswatini, Chad, Togo, Tanzania, Uganda, South Africa and Zimbabwe. The Panel regression technique was used to analyse the data. Both pre-test and post-test were conducted with the aid of E-view-10.

Model specification

To examine the effects of population growth rate, poverty, and COVID-19 on economic growth in Africa ranging from 2020-2022. The dependent variable economic growth was a proxy for Real Gross Domestic Product (RGPD), and the independent variables population growth rate (PGR), the poverty rate (POVR) and COVID-19 were proxies by COVID-19 number of deaths (CND). In line with the work of Zineb, Zineb and Ikram (2022), the model is specified as follows;

The general form of a panel regression model is as follows:

$$RGDP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PGR_{it} + \beta_2 POVR_{it} + \beta_3 CND_{it} + u_{it} + \alpha_i + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where:

$RGDP_{it}$ is the real gross domestic product in country i at time t ,

PGR_{it} is the population growth rate in country i at time t ,

$POVR_{it}$ is the poverty rate in country i at time t ,

CND_{it} is the number of deaths due to COVID-19 in country i at time t ,

β_0 is the intercept

β_1, β_2 and β_3 are the coefficients to be estimated,

u_{it} is the time-invariant individual-specific effect,

α_i is the country-specific intercept (fixed/ random effect),

ϵ_{it} is the error term.

The fixed effects (α_i) control for time-invariant heterogeneity across countries that may be correlated with the independent variables.

The apriori expectations β_1 , β_2 , and $\beta_3 < 0$

Result Presentations

Estimates from the test results are presented and discussed in this section. The panel data statistical properties were analyzed to show the parameters of the variables in the model, while pooled, fixed, and random effects regression were run to reveal how they interact with one another to analyse the effects of population growth rate, poverty, and COVID-19 on economic growth in African countries.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics provide a concise summary of the main characteristics of a dataset. This summary includes measures of central tendency (mean, median, mode), measures of variability (range, variance, standard deviation), and measures of distribution shape (skewness, kurtosis). Measure of normality (Jarque Bera statistics). This summary allows researchers and analysts to quickly understand the basic properties of the data.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the variables

Variables	RGDP	PGR	POVR	CND
Mean	4.89E+10	2.269741	6.94E+10	150834.0
Median	1.51E+10	2.400000	2.26E+10	32609.00
Maximum	4.77E+11	3.700000	1.06E+12	4048580.
Minimum	1.23E+09	-0.300000	0.000000	509.0000
Std. Dev.	9.55E+10	0.780755	1.52E+11	515625.6
Skewness	3.366018	-0.905366	4.493270	6.549927
Kurtosis	13.70751	3.992115	25.40088	46.63445
Jarque-Bera	1.18702	1.18368	2.62507	1.934070
Probability	0.734510	0.823671	0.98219	0.19820
Sum	5.29E+12	245.1320	7.49E+12	16290067
Sum Sq. Dev.	9.76E+23	65.22482	2.47E+24	2.84E+13
Observations	108	108	108	108

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

From Table 1, the p-values for the Jarque-Bera statistics for RGDP, PGR, POVR and CND were 0.734510, 0.823671, 0.98219, and 0.19820 respectively. They were all greater than 0.05. This implies

that the data were normally distributed which indicates that the data can further be processed for policy decisions.

Correlation Matrix

The matrix in Table 2 shows how the variables in the model interact with one another. However, for this study, the emphasis is on the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. The diagonal of the matrix is a set of 1 because the correlation between a variable and itself is always 1. In other words, a correlation matrix is symmetrical. The correlation coefficient ranges between -1 and 1

Table 2. Correlation matrix for the variable

Covariance	RGDP	PGR	POVERTY	CND
Correlation				
RGDP	9.04E+21 1.000000			
PGR	-6.39E+09 -0.086490	0.603933 1.000000		
POVR	1.20E+22 -0.333682	-5.62E+09 -0.047804	2.29E+22 1.000000	
CND	3.03E+16 -0.221233	-117373.0 -0.294279	3.70E+16 0.476301	2.63E+11 1.000000

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

The correlation matrix presented in Table 2 shows a weak negative association between RGDP and PGR, with a correlation coefficient of -0.086490 . The result shows a weak negative relationship between RGDP and POVR, with a correlation coefficient of -0.333682 . It also shows a weak negative relationship between RGDP and CND, with a correlation coefficient approximating -0.221233 . From the correlation matrix, the relationship among the independent variables does not suggest the presence of multi-collinearity, which

indicates that the data can further be processed for policy decisions. This is indicated by the reasonably moderate values of the correlation coefficient

Unit Root Test

To evaluate stationarity or non-stationarity of variables, Lin, Levin, and Chu (LLC) tests were used. The results of the tests for all the variables in the model are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: LLC Unit Root Test

Variables	Statistics	P-Value	Order of Integration
RGDP	-37.2126	0.0000	1(0)
PGR	-30.4613	0.0000	1(0)
POVR	-22.4264	0.0000	1(0)
CND	-2.01913	0.0113	1(0)

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

From Table 3, all the variables RGDP, PGR, POVR, and CND based on LLC Tests, were found the stationary level I (0). Thus, they can be used for further statistical analysis

Co-integration Test

The Kao residual cointegration test was used to test the long run relationships among the variables in table

Table-4 : Kao Residual Cointegration Test

	t-Statistic	Prob.
ADF	-8.649178	0.0000
Residual variance	6.498177	
HAC variance	4.988797	

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

From Table 4, the Panel ADF-Statistic -8.649178 with p-value 0.0000 <0.05, test H0 hypothesis suggesting lack of cointegration is rejected, and cointegration or the existence of long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables of the model is accepted. Thus, the model shows a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables used in the analysis. It shows that the variables move together in the long run.

Panel Regression

In conducting the panel data regression, the pooled, fixed effects, and random effects regression were all estimated in Tables 5,6, and 8 respectively. The redundant fixed effects tests were conducted to choose the best between pooled, and fixed effects regression in table 7. Also, the Hausman test was conducted in Table 9 to choose the best between fixed effects and random effects regression

Table 5. Pooled regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.60E+08	1.51E+10	0.030483	0.9757
PGR	4.35E+09	6.17E+09	0.704683	0.4826
POVR	-0.434695	0.034478	-12.60784	0.0000
CND	-56027.06	10617.80	-5.276712	0.0000
R-squared	0.761152	Mean dependent var		4.89E+10
Adjusted R-squared	0.754262	S.D. dependent var		9.55E+10
S.E. of regression	4.74E+10	Akaike info criterion		52.03614
Sum squared resid	2.33E+23	Schwarz criterion		52.13548
Log likelihood	-2805.952	Hannan-Quinn criter.		52.07642
F-statistic	110.4746	Durbin-Watson stat		1.730644
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

The pooled Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation is presented in Table 5. The pooled OLS regression model with the R2 of 0.761152 means that about 76.11% of the variation in the dependent variable (RGDP) can be explained by the independent variables (PGR, POVR, and CND) the remaining 23.89% can be accounted for the error term. COVID-19(CND) has a negative and significant impact on RGDP. PGR has a positive but insignificant impact on RGDP. POVR has a negative and significant impact on RGDP. The F-statistics 110.47 with a p-value of 0.0000 implies that the population growth rate, poverty, and COVID-19 have a significant impact on economic growth (RGDP) in Africa. The Durbin-Watson test for this model 2.73 implies that there is no autocorrelation among the variables

Table 6. Fixed Effect Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.53E+10	2.02E+10	3.737743	0.0004
PGR	-1.21E+10	8.78E+09	-1.382506	0.1713
POVR	-0.037289	0.007277	-5.124147	0.0000
CND	-2.478028	2919.539	-8.487739	0.0000

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.997550	Mean dependent var	4.89E+10
Adjusted R-squared	0.996200	S.D. dependent var	9.55E+10
S.E. of regression	5.89E+09	Akaike info criterion	48.10473
Sum squared resid	2.39E+21	Schwarz criterion	49.07327
Log likelihood	-2558.655	Hannan-Quinn criter.	48.49744
F-statistic	739.1924	Durbin-Watson stat	2.294417
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

The fixed effect estimation is presented in Table 6. The fixed effect regression model seems to fit the data reasonably well with the R2 of 0.99550 meaning that about 99.76% of the variation in the dependent variable (RGDP) can be explained by the independent variables (PGR, POVR, and CND) the remaining 0.24% can be accounted to error term, this implies that the model is a good fit. PGR has a negative but insignificant impact on RGDP. COVID-19 has a negative and significant relationship with RGDP POVR has a negative but significant impact on RGDP. The F-statistics 739.19 with a p-value of 0.0000 implies that the population growth rate, poverty, and COVID-19 have a significant impact on economic growth (RGDP) in Africa. The Durbin-Watson test for this model 2.3 implies that there is no autocorrelation among the variables

Further analysis to check if fixed cross-section effects alone are necessary for the panel regression, a redundant fixed-cross section effect test was employed. The null hypothesis is that the fixed effects are redundant and thus unnecessary. The result of the redundant test is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	190.187095	(35,69)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	494.592721	35	0.0000

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

The likelihood ratio test of the redundant fixed effect for cross-sectional effect shows that the use of fixed-effects estimation is adequate as the null hypothesis of redundant fixed effect was rejected at 5 percent level of significance. Since the p-value (0.000) < 0.05. This implies that the fixed effect result is better than the pooled OLS.

Table 8. Random Effect result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.75E+10	4.43E+09	3.949940	0.0001
PGR	4.74E+09	1.81E+09	2.617146	0.0102
POVR	0.163224	0.006165	26.47535	0.0000
CND	62168.46	2062.270	30.14564	0.0000
Effects Specification				
			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			7.55E+09	0.6219
Idiosyncratic random			5.89E+09	0.3781
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.430336	Mean dependent var		2.01E+10
Adjusted R-squared	0.413903	S.D. dependent var		3.99E+10
S.E. of regression	3.06E+10	Sum squared resid		9.72E+22
F-statistic	26.18788	Durbin-Watson stat		1.862792
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Unweighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.587199	Mean dependent var		4.89E+10
Sum squared resid	4.03E+23	Durbin-Watson stat		1.808004

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

The random effect is presented in Table 8. The random effect regression model with the R2 of 0.430336 means that about 43.03% of the variation in the dependent variable (RGDP) can be explained by the independent variables (PGR, POVR, and CND) the remaining 56.97% can be accounted for the error term. PGR, POVR, and CND have a positive and significant relationship with RGDP. The F-statistics 26.19 with a p-value of 0.0.0000 implies that the population growth rate, poverty, and COVID-19 have insignificant impacts on economic growth in Africa. The Durbin-Watson test for this model 1.8 implies that there is no autocorrelation among the variable

Table 9. Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq.		
	Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	5.745086	3	0.1247

Source: Authors Computation, 2023(Eview-10)

The Hausman test is presented in Table 9 to find whether the random-effects model or the fixed-effects model is the most appropriate method to conduct the panel regression. The p-value (0.1247) of the Husman test is greater than 0.05($p > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted which means the fixed effect model is a better choice. That is null hypothesis of model 1 is accepted in favour of fixed effects. The reports the regression results of the different panel analyses, based on the various diagnostic tests (redundant fixed and Hausman test) above, the regression was estimated as a fixed-effect model. Hence, the results discussed below are based on the fixed-effect model.

Discussion of Findings

The result from Table 6 indicated that the population growth rate has a negative but insignificant impact on economic growth in Africa. A unit increase in PGR will lead -1.21 unit decrease in economic growth in Africa and vice versa. This finding does not agree with the work of Byaro, et al (2023) that rapid population growth positively affected domestic investments in SSA.

The result in Table 6 also indicated that poverty (POVR) has a negative but significant impact on economic growth in Africa (RGDP). A unit increase in POVR will lead to a -0.037 unit decrease in economic growth in Africa and vice versa. This finding agrees with the work of Zhu, Bashir, and Marie (2022) that negative impact is concentrated at high poverty levels. Advocates for poverty reduction policies, emphasizing their positive impact on economic growth.

Lastly, the result in Table 6 also revealed that COVID-19 has a negative and significant impact on economic growth in Africa. A unit increase in CND will lead to a -2.48 unit decrease in economic growth in Africa and vice versa. This finding agreed with the work of Gagnon, Kamin, and Kearns (2023) that COVID-19 deaths had a small effect; lockdown stringency significantly influenced GDP.

Conclusion

The findings of this study underscore the detrimental effects of both poverty and the COVID-19 pandemic on economic growth in Africa. The negative and significant impact observed highlights the urgent need for targeted and comprehensive interventions to address these challenges. The economic repercussions of poverty and the ongoing health crisis have far-reaching consequences, affecting various sectors and impeding overall progress.

Moreover, while the population growth rate was found to hurt economic growth, the insignificance of this effect suggests that other factors might be more influential in shaping the economic landscape. Nevertheless, acknowledging the intricate interplay between population dynamics and economic development remains crucial for formulating effective policies. In conclusion, a multifaceted and coordinated approach is necessary to overcome the negative impacts of poverty, the COVID-19 pandemic, and demographic factors on economic growth in Africa. Policymakers, international organizations, and local communities must work together to implement and sustain effective strategies that promote inclusive and sustainable development.

Recommendations

- **Poverty Alleviation Programs:** Implement and strengthen poverty alleviation programs that address the root causes of poverty, such as lack of access to education, healthcare, and employment opportunities. These programs should be designed to promote inclusive growth and empower vulnerable populations.
- **Healthcare Infrastructure and Pandemic Preparedness:** Enhance healthcare infrastructure and invest in pandemic preparedness to mitigate the impact of future health crises. Strengthening healthcare systems, ensuring equitable access to vaccines, and promoting public health measures are essential components of a resilient response.
- **Economic Diversification:** Encourage economic diversification to reduce dependence on specific sectors and enhance overall economic resilience. Diversification can create new opportunities for growth and help countries navigate external shocks more effectively.
- **Education and Skill Development:** Prioritize education and skill development initiatives to enhance human capital. A well-educated and skilled workforce is crucial for innovation, productivity, and overall economic development.
- **Population Policies:** While the study found an insignificant impact of population growth rate on economic growth, it is important for policymakers to monitor demographic trends. Implementing responsible population policies that promote family planning and address demographic challenges can contribute to sustainable development.
- **International Collaboration:** Foster international collaboration and cooperation to address common challenges, such as poverty and pandemics. Engaging in partnerships for knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and joint initiatives can amplify the impact of efforts to promote economic growth in the region.

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